

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

On farm research: do's and don'ts

On-farm research is valuable for finding out how research methods work in actual field and farm scale. At the same time, moving from controlled lab and test plots to field scale presents new challenges because of within-field variability. Here's a few experience led guidelines:

- Do a randomized block replication: Make at least 4 strips in the field. Each strip shall have all the treatments in randomized order (roll a dice, toss a coin, or take a list of random numbers)
- Check the field variability before deciding the strip direction and placing. Drainage maps, Sentinel-2 vegetation indices, yield monitor maps, topography and soil type are all important.
- Mark the plot boundaries on the field, in an easy to see way, which can be noticed even when the crop is there, and which do not damage harvesting equipment (discuss with machinery owners/drivers). Wooden or plastic poles are good, as is plowing a berm, putting in perennial grass or drilling a row of flowers. Anything that can prevent treatments slipping to each other is great.
- Make the strips to match machinery width multiples (i.e. 20 m, not 19 m), also make them wide enough (avoid edge effect).
- Make a map of the treatments, give it to the tractor operator. It's easiest to run all replicates of a certain treatment to their test plots first, and then switch to the second treatment. GPS guidance makes this easy.
- If you have continuous data (yield monitor etc.), it makes sense to split each strip lengthwise and do a pairwise comparison on each subsection
- Don't just split the field in half in the middle
- Don't forget to write field operations down
- Don't assume that soil type would be uniform, also in the subsoil
- Don't assume that drainage works

1. Fields have variability and replicated random strips are one way to control it.

KEYWORDS

On-farm experiments, replicated trials, design, analysis

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